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Social and Emotional Learning Through Game-Based Learning: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: There is a trend in educational research that indicates the increasing interest about digital games' influence on learning. In addition, numerous studies have been conducted particularly on the effects of game-based learning across disciplines. Thus, this systematic literature review of current research searched the empirical evidence regarding the effects of game-based learning on social and emotional learning. This study followed the "PRISMA framework" in selecting the research articles for the study. Social and emotional learning were identified and categorized through the "CASEL Framework". Eighteen articles found to be eligible for qualitative synthesis were analyzed accordingly. This research also categorized the research articles according to the year of publication, outlets of publication, location of the study, research design used, game-genre and social and emotional learning outcome. Empirical indication of the effects of game-based learning on social and emotional learning were seen to be evident among the participants of each study. Several outcomes were found, such as participants developing competencies on self-awareness and management, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision making. Specific capacities for each competency were also found among the participants. The researcher assumes the potential of game-based learning on the development of social and emotional skills of students. Thus, a follow-up study in the local context is suggested.

Keywords: *game-based learning, gamification, social and emotional learning, gamification, CASEL Framework*

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Introduction

Social and emotional skills are an integral part of human development that need attention, especially with the complexity of today's environment (CASEL, n.d.). With the world's current situation, this complex environment can be associated with the increasing demand for collaboration and communication. In this regard, the process of interaction, socialization, and workplace communication and collaboration rapidly transform into a new realm that might be exceptionally different from the world we live in today (Microsoft Learn, 2022). In order to cope with this set up, social and emotional skills are necessary to capacitate the future generation with flexibility and fresh perspectives to function at work in times of life and work challenges such as change, uncertainty, pressure, and stress (McKinsey Global Institute, 2017). Thus, education systems should provide opportunities to develop skills associated with social and emotional learning such as self-awareness and management, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision making (CASEL, n.d.).

Alongside changes in the requirements of the environment, the younger generation adapts their lifestyle to fit these, such as changes in technology (Dimitra, 2020). Technological advancements such as digitalization have brought the world a new realm of possibilities, especially in the field of education (Shadiev et al., 2018). The growing domain of digitalization has brought about technological implications in the digital world (Sa & Serpa, 2022). For instance, digital game-based learning has garnered increasing attention in educational technology where digital games are utilized to fill in the gaps between educational objectives and assessment (Hung et al., 2018). Utilizing digital games in education emphasizes changes in students' practices as they take involvement in the learning process (Obery et al., 2021). Digital games are said to provide students an opportunity to explore and connect gaming contexts into an authentic, conceptual understanding of educational materials (Martin et al., 2019).

Digital game-based learning improves student outcomes across many areas (Stieler-Hunt & Jones, 2019). For instance, it has been proven to be effective in improving English communication skills through a "flipped contextual game-based learning" methodology (Lin et al., 2018). This coincides with the findings that there are positive effects of mobile game-based approach to student learning in mathematics (Juric et al., 2018). Further, 3D programmable charades game is said to have increased students' development of computational thinking and practices in multidisciplinary contexts (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2021). In terms of cultural learning, game-based learning is said to provide significant improvements in students' achievement, knowledge retention, and motivation. Students' perception of technology tends to be positive (Lin et al., 2018). The following studies support how powerful digital tools are for learning in different disciplines and their potential as supplementary instruction.

Provided that a selection of studies prove that game-based learning supports several types of learning across disciplines, the researcher aims to clarify whether game-based learning can improve students' social and emotional learning. In recent years, talks about educational policies related to improving students' social and emotional skills have increased. However, there is uncertainty in implementing clear-cut policies due to the changing education landscape, and much depends on the priority of academic leaders and administrators. This position may be attributed to a lack of comprehensive metrics identifying the success of social and emotional learning inside the classroom (OECD, 2021). Thus, the researcher of this study would like to identify the connection

between social and emotional skills through game-based learning.

Review of Related Literature

Definition of game-based learning

Game-based learning (GBL) is an approach to learning where the game played and its content enhances knowledge (Kirriemuir & McFarlane, 2004). Likewise, it is an approach to learning that uses digital and fun activities that adhere to educational objectives and assessment (Hung et al., 2018). This approach aims to address learning barriers such as learning difficulties, low levels of motivation, lack of engagement and interaction, and other mental health problems (Yukselturk et al., 2018). In addition, game-based learning utilizes games as an effective learning tool and for other educational purposes; games have the power to provide a virtual world for learning that encourages engagement (Gee, 2003). *Social and emotional learning and CASEL Framework*

Social and emotional learning (SEL) is an approach to learning where a person develops skills in managing their emotions, builds positive relationships, rationally solves problems and makes reliable decisions in life (Zins, 2004). SEL is said to greatly impact the foundational development of a child until adulthood (National Research Council and Institute of Medicine, 2000). Social competence as a subdomain is defined as the ability of a person to be effective in social interactions such as making connections, collaborative and cooperative skills, and flexibility and adaptability in the demands of various social systems (Fabes & Gaertner, 2006). On the other hand, emotional competence is the ability of a person to understand and regulate one's own emotions and the ability to be empathetic to the emotional and behavioral cues of others. It also entails understanding the consequence of being expressive of one's own emotions (Denham, 2006). Thus, social and emotional competencies are said to be essential foundations of children's holistic development and potential successes (Halle & Darling-Churchhill, 2016)

Several researchers and educational psychology practitioners have a substantial interest in studying this domain, specifically the ways on how it is developed and assessed to track peoples' well-being and the effectiveness of interventions related to it (Darling-Churchill & Lippman, 2016). One organization that created a social and emotional learning framework, known as the CASEL framework, is the CASEL Organization. The CASEL framework is said to be a foundation for applying evidence-based SEL strategies to communities. Also known as the "CASEL wheel", it helps cultivate skills and environments that advance students' learning development. This framework can be applied to encourage cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills across five areas of competence. This foundational concept can nurture an equitable environment for students; educators can use cases across four key settings that strengthen students' social, emotional, and academic development. This framework includes "CASEL 5," which are broad and interrelated areas of competence, namely self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making; these competencies have specific capacities listed (CASEL, n.d.).

Effects of game-based approach on social and emotional learning

Several studies show the influence of game-based learning in different areas. In a study

(Yeh et al., 2020), game-based learning was seen to have significantly improved students' positive relationship among their peers, flow experience, and self-determination. In another study, positive relations through collaboration were also seen to be positively affected by game-based learning's scripted collaboration (van der Meiji et al., 2020). However, a study debunks this claim by declaring that game-based learning is not as effective if a certain appropriate collaboration guideline is not present (Wang, 2020). Although in a different study regarding environmental behaviors through collaboration and individual game play, collaborative environment is seen to increase attitudinal learning; thus, collaboration plays a part in the effects of game-based learning (Li & Chu, 2021). There are also studies that connect literacy and analytical thinking to game-based learning. With regards to reading literacy, a study of reading skills gamification (Yeh et al., 2020) suggests that students' profound engagement with gamified reading platforms can increase reading motivation. In one study on number literacy, no significant difference in students' math motivation was found after a game-based learning intervention (Es-Sajjade & Paas, 2020). On the contrary, a study on the impact of game-based learning approach on attitudes in math found that there is a significant increase in students' affective-motivational state in mathematics after an intervention using a mathematics game (Chen, 2020). Empathy and compassion were also seen to be enhanced by game-based learning through a role-playing video game (Schrier, 2017). The following studies reveal opposing views on the effects of the approach on social and emotional competency. Thus, the researcher would like to seek answers to the research question of this study.

Research question

Education research trends indicate that there is an increasing interest about digital games' influence on learning. In addition, several explorations have been performed, particularly on the effects of game-based learning across disciplines (Qian & Clark, 2016). Nevertheless, a thorough review of existing literature is needed to evaluate the possibilities of game-based learning to develop social and emotional learning. The aim of this study is to establish existing empirical evidence concerning the significant effects of game-based learning on social and emotional learning. The findings will provide significant support for game-based learning as an approach and framework, which is intended to support students' social and emotional skill development.

Methodology

Key words and database search strategy

The researcher conducted a keyword search through EBSCO host Search Engine-Multidisciplinary Research Data Base. A Boolean/phrase search mode was done to the keywords used: "game-based learning" OR "digital game-based learning" OR "digital games" OR "mobile games" AND "socio-emotional learning" OR "social and emotional learning" OR "social-emotional literacy". This resulted in 3,942 research articles.

Selection of research articles for inclusion

The criteria for selecting the research papers to be included in this study is centered upon the PRISMA Framework (Moher et al., 2009). The selection is focused on research papers regarding game-based learning and social and emotional learning. Specifically, the search was limited to only one database, which is the Academic Search Complete; the

rest of the databases in EBSCO Host were excluded. The researcher limited the papers to those published from 2017 up to 2022. In addition, the researcher identified other inclusion criteria. The following criteria are: (a) Include academic journal for publication only; (b) Include papers in the English language only; (c) Include research articles in full PDF; (d) Include articles from select journals related to education psychology and education technology. These inclusion criteria brought the initial number of articles down to 129 articles.

Quality assessment of research papers

The researcher further analyzed the 129 research articles that met the inclusion criteria. A qualitative analysis was done to further identify eligible articles for this study. All duplicate articles were removed. The abstract of the articles was thoroughly analyzed to ensure its relevance to the subject matter. After a thorough assessment of the abstracts, the researcher found only 35 eligible articles.

General findings

Thirty-five research articles that have passed the inclusion criteria were thoroughly assessed by the researcher to ensure that the variables being undertaken in the study were specific to the research questions. The researcher also ensured that quantitative evidence to support the aim of this study is presented among the research articles. Hence, the researcher selected 18 articles to be included in the study. A PRISMA Flow Chart is presented in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Figure 1

PRISMA Flow Chart of the Study

Findings and Discussion

Data extracted were presented and analyzed based on the year of publication, outlets of publication, location of the study, research design used, game-genre and social and emotional learning outcome.

Location of the study

Analysis of the 18 studies showed that the majority were published in Taiwan with 50% of the publication coming from the location. Figure 2 shows the rest of the countries having one published article.

Figure 2

Location of the Study

Eligibility criteria of this study excluded published articles before September 2017. Among the 18 research articles, six were published in 2020. Five articles were published in 2021; 2017 and 2018 both have three articles published in each year. and the least number was in 2019 with only 1 article published. Only one article was published in 2019.

Figure 3

Year of Publication

There are five journal titles included in the study. *Educational Technology Research & Development* has the greatest number of research articles included in this study with six research articles. The *British Journal of Educational Technology* has two articles included; the *Journal of Educational Technology & Society* has three. The *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* has two and both *TechTrends: Linking Research & Practice to Improve Learning* and *Behaviour & Information Technology* has one each.

Table 1

Outlets of Publication

	Count of Papers	Study
Educational Technology Research & Development	6	(Chang, Kao, Hwang, & Lin, 2020) (Mavridis, Katmada., & Tsiatsos, 2020) (Chen C.-H. , 2020) (Chang, Chung, & Chang, 2020) (Vandercruysse, et al., 2017) (Schrier, 2017)
British Journal of Educational Technology	5	(Hwang, Chien, & Li, 2021) (van der Meij, Veldkamp, & Leemkuil, 2020) (Li & Chu, 2021) (Liang, Hsu, & Hwang, 2021) (Hanghøj, Lieberoth, & Misfeldt, 2018)
Journal of Educational Technology & Society	3	(Lin, et al., 2018) (Chu, Chen, Kuo, & Yang, 2021) (Yükseltürk, Altıok, & Başer, 2018)
International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction	2	(Yeh, Sai, & Chuang, 2020) (Chen, Lu, & Lu, 2019)
TechTrends: Linking Research & Practice to Improve Learning	1	(Janakiraman, Watson, & Watson, 2021)
Behaviour & Information Technology	1	(Paule-Ruiz, Álvarez-García, Pérez-Pérez, Álvarez-Sierra, & Trespalacios-Menéndez, 2017)

Figure 4

Research Design Used

Analysis of the 18 research articles revealed that seven research articles identified their design as experimental. Another seven stated that their design is quasi-experimental. Although quasi-experimental is another type of experimental design, only seven research articles stated their specific design used. Three research articles are categorized to have used the mixed method design; one mixed method article specified its design to be longitudinal. Specific research articles of each design are presented in Table 1.

Table 2 shows the research designs used and the specific research articles that are classified under each category.

Table 2

<i>Research Design Used</i>		
Research Design	Count of Papers	Study
Experimental	7	(Yeh, Sai, & Chuang, 2020) (van der Meij, Veldkamp, & Leemkuil, 2020) (Chen C.-H. , 2020) (Chang, Chung, & Chang, 2020) (Hanghøj, Lieberoth, & Misfeldt, 2018) (Vandercruysse, et al., 2017) (Schrier, 2017)
Quasi-experimental	7	(Hwang, Chien, & Li, 2021) (Lin, et al., 2018) (Chu, Chen, Kuo, & Yang, 2021) (Chang, Kao, Hwang, & Lin, 2020) (Mavridis, Katmada., & Tsiatsos, 2020) (Liang, Hsu, & Hwang, 2021) (Yükseltürk, Altrok, & Başer, 2018)
Mixed method	3	(Janakiraman, Watson, & Watson, 2021) (Chen, Lu, & Lu, 2019) (Paule-Ruiz, Álvarez-García, Pérez-Pérez, Álvarez-Sierra, & Trespalacios-Menéndez, 2017)
Mixed method-longitudinal	1	(Li & Chu, 2021)

Game Genre

Game genres used in research articles were also categorized. In Figure 5, the most frequently used game genre was role playing game (RPG) with seven papers. Education games, also known as serious games, were used five times. Virtual reality and simulation were used twice and both mobile game and consoles once.

Figure 5

Game Genre

Social and emotional learning domain outcome

The most significant data that answer the research question (whether game-based learning has a significant effect on social and emotional learning) are presented in Figure 1. The SEL outcome for each study was categorized according to CASEL Framework’s areas of competence. Analysis of the 18 research articles revealed that nine of the research articles showed that there was a significant increase in self-management competency among participants of game-based learning. Social awareness was also seen in three research articles and self-awareness in two research articles. Responsible decision-making and relationship skill were identified in one research article. Two outcomes of mixed competence were seen in two research articles, with a mix of relationship skills and self-awareness outcome and mixed self-awareness and self-management outcome.

Figure 1

Social and Emotional Learning Domain Outcomes

It presents each broad area of SEL competence specified into different capacities. The most frequent SEL capacity identified among the participants of game-based learning was exhibiting discipline and self-motivation, which is classified under self-management competency.

Table 3

Specific Social and Emotional Learning Capacities in Each Research Article

SEL Outcome	Count of Papers	Study
“Exhibiting self-discipline and self-motivation”	7	(Chang, Kao, Hwang, & Lin, 2020) (Mavridis, Katmada., & Tsiatsos, 2020) (Chen C.-H. , 2020) (Chang, Chung, & Chang, 2020) (Vandercruysse, et al., 2017) (Paule-Ruiz, Álvarez-García, Pérez-

			Pérez, Álvarez-Sierra, & Trespalcios-Menéndez, 2017) (Lin, et al., 2018)
“Experiencing self-efficacy”	2		(Chu, Chen, Kuo, & Yang, 2021) (Yükseltürk, Altıok, & Başer, 2018)
“Understanding the influences of organizations/systems on behavior”	2		(Janakiraman, Watson, & Watson, 2021) (Hanghøj, Lieberoth, & Misfeldt, 2018)
“Demonstrating curiosity and open-mindedness”	1		(Liang, Hsu, & Hwang, 2021)
“Exhibiting self-discipline and self-motivation & demonstrating personal and collective agency”	1		(Chen, Lu, & Lu, 2019)
“Demonstrating empathy and compassion”	1		(Schrier, 2017)
“Experiencing self-efficacy and Exhibiting self-discipline and self-motivation”	1		(Hwang, Chien, & Li, 2021)
“Demonstrating personal and collective agency”	1		(Yeh, Sai, & Chuang, 2020)
“Communicating effectively & Practicing teamwork and collaborative problem-solving”	1		(van der Meij, Veldkamp, & Leemkuil, 2020)
“Developing positive relationships & experiencing self-efficacy”	1		(Li & Chu, 2021)

Discussion

The research articles included were published in five different countries. Taiwan dominated the publishing of articles related to game-based learning and its effect on social and emotional learning. USA, Spain, Turkey, Belgium, China, India, Denmark, Netherlands, and Greece have one article each. In the Global Games Market Report, among the 10 countries with the largest revenue estimates in 2022, only USA, which ranks second globally, has a published research article included in this study (Newzoo, 2022). Regarding the year of publication, most of the research articles were published 2020 onwards. Game-based learning was employed at the start of the pandemic as an alternative educational practice and to supplement learning. This was seen as a strategic solution to the growing challenges during the pandemic, given that educational institutions needed to immediately adapt to the world’s existing conditions (Wati, 2020). Various education technology and human development-related journal articles were included in this research. These published articles were selected for this study to align the following topics with each other: methods of teaching, education technology, human development, and social sciences.

In terms of research design, experimental design was the most dominant design found among the research articles. Mostly, the research articles involved quantitative analyses of participants' learning outcomes after an intervention with game-based learning. Specifically, seven articles were categorized under the experimental design. Furthermore, seven research articles were categorized as quasi-experimental in design, which is another type of research design that utilizes a pre-test post-test framework. A mixed method of both qualitative and quantitative design was also found in four research articles where the significant relationship of variables was measured through tests and interviews (Fraenkel et al, 2012). Various game genres were used in the research articles. Mostly, games used were categorized as role-playing games and serious or educational games. The games used as part of the intervention in some articles were specifically designed or developed for that specific research only.

Given that the CASEL framework has classified broad areas of competence, outcomes of each game-based learning intervention were categorized accordingly. Analysis of the research articles found that most of the research articles have targeted self-management competence that also aimed at the capacity of the participants to show self-discipline and motivation as well as demonstrating one's own and collective agency. In addition, the social awareness competence of the participants was targeted by developing empathy and compassion towards others and knowing that organizations have influences on one's behavior. Self-awareness was also targeted by developing participants' skills to develop self-efficacy. Relationship skills were also hit by giving students the opportunity to solve problems through teamwork, growing positive relationships and effective communication. Lastly, responsible decision making was developed by encouraging curiosity and open mindedness among the participants. This research found that all social and emotional competences were developed in the game-based learning interventions.

Conclusion

This systematic literature review about the significant effects of game-based learning on students' social and emotional learning revealed that there are empirical evidence validating the effects of game-based learning on both research variables. Analysis of the 18 research articles revealed that participants of each study that have undergone game-based learning found significant increases on their social and emotional learning competency after the intervention. Although social and emotional learning targeted in these studies may have resulted in different targeted competencies, the framework that guides this categorization specifically states the interrelatedness of the competencies mentioned in this study. In summary, the researcher assumes that game-based learning has the potential to improve the social and emotional skills of the students.

Limitations and Recommendations

This systematic literature review about the significant effects of game-based learning on students' social and emotional learning has several limitations. The researcher placed certain eligibility criteria that limited the scope of this research. Some of these limitations are including research articles published from 2017-2022 only and including research articles that only show quantitative values. The number of keywords searched were also limited to: "game-based learning" OR "digital game-based learning" OR "digital games" OR "mobile games" AND "socio-emotional learning" OR "social and emotional learning" OR "social-emotional literacy". This might have resulted in finding fewer articles. Further,

the researcher chose to select specific databases for this search. Likewise, only six journals were selected to ensure that they fit the criteria for selection.

The researcher recommends adding more keywords to explore more journal articles related to the study. The range of years the research articles were published could have been increased so that more related and significant articles in the last decade could be included. Journal titles could have been omitted as an eligibility criterion as some of the relevant research articles for this study could have been neglected. Nevertheless, the researcher would like to seek further studies related to this topic. The researcher found no local studies regarding game-based learning and its effect on social and emotional learning. Thus, no empirical evidence was found whether this approach is effective in the development of social and emotional skills of students in the local context. Provided that the pandemic has pushed institutions to try virtual and hybrid learning, which subsequently encouraged teachers to explore digital games to supplement students' learning, there should be follow-up research as to its effectiveness, especially in the social and emotional learning skills of students.

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